

SMART PLANNER EVENT MANAGEMENT WEB APPLICATION

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Background

Organization and Business Domain

Event management industry is the emerging business domain that has a great rising demand nowadays. Since the Internet plays an important role in this event management industry, there are multiple opportunities to grow up, in this business domain at local and international levels. People celebrate events which are related to the personal and the corporate world events such as weddings, birthday parties, corporate events etc. Planning those events have always been a long process that involves a lot of time, money, effort, stress, and high risks. Because of that reasons, people tend to hand over those responsibilities to another party. Therefore, planning agents, event management companies, websites, and mobile applications are coming up as a solution.

Overview of the Existing System

Currently most of this kind of event management application were manual or semi-automated. Event management companies are the entities who plan the whole event. Customers must contact that companies and give their requirements to those companies. They organize everything according to the customer requirements. It is very costly because service charge of that companies is very high. There are many websites related to the Event planning and management, but those websites basically provide static information regarding event planning and vendors who were available to get services.

When it comes to the Mobile Applications most of them developed are available only within specific countries or region. Also, using those applications only could plan one event per time. To address those limitations identified, this project discusses the development of Smart Planner Event Management Web Application that will assist people in organizing their events based on their preferences and budget

System Analysis

Problem Analysis

According to the current system analysis there were few major problems identified. They are,

- No ability to plan more than one event using one application
- No common online platform to communicate between planners and vendors directly
- Most applications are country specific and not available globally.
- No ability to get details about previous events that were organized by service providers,
- No platform to connect with previous customers and share experience with new customers
- No way of rating vendors regarding their service quality.

This proposed system is going to be a web application which is available and accessible from anywhere in the world. The main aim of this system is to provide facilities for planners to plan more than one event as they require and needs to make sure that their events goes smoothly according to their plans. Also, it aims to create platform for vendors to trade and advertise their products and services.

Requirement Analysis

There were three main users of this application such as planner, vendor, and administrator. So, there are three base modules: Administrator module,

Vendor Module, Planner module. Each module consists with functions which regards to each user interactions with this application.

Also, when developing smart planner, it considered non-functional requirements such as performance requirements, safety requirements, and security requirements and some quality attributes such as reliability, availability, maintainability, portability, reusability, extensibility, and accessibility.

System Development

System development was done under the Agile software development methodologies since the system was developed as series of versions and iterations occurred across the activities. Multi layered architecture for web application was used as system architecture design which comprises of three layers such as Presentation, Business and Database.

Technologies such as Bootstrap version 4.3.1, HTML, CSS and JavaScript used for the front-end development, and PHP and MySQL were used for the Back-end Development. Here Visual Studio Code IDE was used as code developer, MySQL (on WampServer) was used as database management server environment and Firefox web browser was used for testing and previewing web application.

Conclusion

Smart Planner web application was developed to reduce the time, cost and risk involved in the processes of planning and preparing of any event. It provides one common platform for planners and vendors to connect and an online platform for vendors to trade and advertise their products and services. Here planners having their full freedom to plan multiple events on the same platform according to their preference which was an added advantage.

Since Smart Planner developed and tested locally, by hosting this application with real server environment will make it accessible worldwide. Also developing Smart planner as a mobile application give more opportunity to attract target audience. Here it will increase the applicability and usage of the web application with some UI and functionality improvements.

References

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